

kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha were applied. Prilled urea was applied as basal in 2-3 cm standing water.

Root zone placement (10-12 cm) of urea supergranules (USG) and basal sulfur-coated-urea (SCU) and Mussooriephos-coated urea (MPCU) at

58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha were evaluated against local best split (1/2 basal + 1/4 at maximum tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation) and standard best split (2/3 basal + 1/3 at panicle initiation).

Maximum grain yield was with USG and SCU at all N levels (see table). USG

produced significantly higher yields than standard best split urea and MPCU at 87 and 116 kg N/ha. USG and SCU also produced significantly more panicles/m² than MPCU at 116 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen management for increasing N efficiency in transplanted rice

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We compared the efficiency of a single application of sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and split application of prilled urea (PU) at

varying levels of N during 1983 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Treatments were SCU, USG, and PU at 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha. Medium-duration, dwarf variety Usha was the test crop. Soil was a Vertisol (clay-loam, with 210.11 kg available N, 12.50 kg available P, 225 kg available K/ha, 0.20 mmho EC, 0.60% organic C, and pH 6.5-7.5).

Growth and yield-contributing characters were significantly superior with SCU and USG (see table). Grain

and straw yields were significantly different with different forms and levels of N.

Maximum grain yield was with SCU, followed by USG. SCU and USG were similar in N efficiency. USG produced a significantly higher straw yield than SCU and PU.

N at 116 kg/ha produced significantly high grain and straw yields. □

Grain yield and ancillary characters as influenced by sources and levels of N. Raipur, India, 1983 kharif.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Sources and methods of N application	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Sound spikelets/panicle
0	Check	1.9	2.30	190	1.3	17	48
29	Urea, best split	2.6	2.94	206	1.7	18	62
29	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.2	3.51	259	2.1	20	69
29	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.2	3.77	257	1.8	19	66
	Mean	3.0	3.40	240	1.9	19	65
58	Urea, best split	3.0	3.15	243	1.9	19	67
58	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.8	4.35	304	2.2	21	76
58	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.7	4.97	303	2.1	20	70
	Mean	3.5	4.16	283	2.1	20	71
87	Urea, best split	3.3	3.50	277	1.9	19	68
87	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.2	5.30	344	2.3	21	79
87	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.1	5.84	340	2.2	21	76
	Mean	3.9	4.88	320	2.2	20	75
116	Urea, best split	3.7	4.32	335	2.1	20	72
116	SCU broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.5	6.24	409	2.5	22	82
116	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.3	6.97	405	2.4	22	80
	Mean	4.2	5.84	383	2.3	21	78
	CD (0.05) for forms	0.2	0.40	9	0.1	0.4	5.7
	for levels	0.2	0.46	10	0.2	0.5	6.6

Nitrogen sources for flooded rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU), neem cake coated-urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), didin-coated urea (DCU), and urea supergranule (USG) at 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for transplanted rice in the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons. Experimental field soil was a fine, silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Hapludoll with pH

Effect of N source and N level on yield. Pantnagar, India, 1983 and 1984 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Mean
<i>N sources</i>			
PU	3.67	3.71	3.69
NCU	4.36	4.57	4.46
LCU	3.79	4.14	3.96
DCU	3.71	4.11	3.91
USG	4.70	4.73	4.72
SE	0.06	0.06	—
CD (0.05)	0.16	0.16	—
<i>N levels (kg/ha)</i>			
0	2.25	2.42	2.33
40	3.36	3.55	3.45
80	4.11	4.36	4.24
120	4.66	4.91	4.78
SE	0.04	0.04	—
CD (0.05)	0.12	0.12	—